

Title: Challenges in Geographical Image Classification Using CNNs: The Impact of Visual Similarities and the Case for Metadata Integration

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have become essential tools in a variety of applications, including image classification. This paper focuses on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and the challenges associated with feature extraction in image classification tasks, particularly in distinguishing between images from different countries. While CNNs automate feature extraction, they may overlook critical, location-specific features such as poles, bollocks or license plates, which are crucial for accurate classification. This research addresses these limitations by exploring the potential benefits of integrating metadata into the classification process. Through extensive experimentation with various custom and pre-trained CNN models, we observed an average accuracy of around 50% when classifying images from four distinct countries (Russia, Australia, Argentina and Brazil). This research addresses the consequences of these findings, emphasizing the importance of adding metadata to improve model performance and classification accuracy. This research proposes leveraging metadata to enhance classification accuracy by integrating distinctive location-specific cues. Although the implementation of metadata integration was constrained by available resources, this study highlights the potential benefits of using metadata to improve classification performance. By throwing light on these problems, we want to contribute insights into enhancing CNN based image categorization for geographically comparable images

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1 Introduction

CNNs are extremely useful in image processing and computer vision because they are able to automatically extract features from images. They mimic the visual cortex of animals by using convolutional filters to detect local patterns. CNNs use shared weights and local connections to reduce the number of parameters, making them efficient for training. [1]

Other deep learning systems, such as Recursive Neural Networks (RvNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), have showed promise in specialised applications such as natural language processing and speech recognition.

CNNs outperform these networks, particularly in jobs involving picture data. Weight sharing, sparse interactions, and parameter sharing are all advantages that are contributing to lower network complexity and faster training periods. [1]

However, challenges remain in classifying images of geographically similar locations due to the limitations of automated feature extraction. This study investigates the effectiveness of CNNs in geographic image classification and the potential benefits of integrating metadata. By comparing various custom and pre-trained CNN models, we aim to highlight the necessity of metadata for improved classification accuracy.

2 Related Works

2.1 Challenges of Reliable Image Geolocation: An accurate image Geolocation is difficult because of the wide range of landscapes, structures, and ecosystems. Visual similarities between sites, obscured vistas, seasonal changes, and low-quality photos can all reduce geolocation accuracy. Furthermore, the absence of distinguishing characteristics or contextual signals in some photographs hampers the procedure. [2]

2.2 Image Localizability Detection: Image localizability refers to the ability of an image to be accurately geolocated based on its content. Detecting localizability is crucial for improving geolocation systems, as some images may not contain sufficient information for reliable location predictions. Selective prediction methodologies have been proposed to allow models to identify non-localizable images and restrict from making predictions on them. This strategy improves the overall geolocation performance by focusing on images that are more likely to be accurately geolocated. [2]

In the context of our dataset, which consists of images from geographically similar regions like jungles, mountains, and roads, localizability becomes a significant challenge. Such environments often exhibit visually similar characteristics, making it difficult for CNN models to distinguish between images from different locations.

2.3 Integration of Multiple Cues: PlaNet improves accuracy by incorporating many cues from photos. This integration is accomplished using a deep CNN architecture that learns to recognise and combine multiple cues to provide exact position predictions. Unlike prior efforts that relied on global image descriptors or landmark recognition, PlaNet's model is intended to exploit and synthesise a broader variety of visual information, hence improving its capacity to discern the geographic context of photographs. [3]

2.4 GeoWINE: It is a geolocation-based retrieval system that integrates multiple data sources, including text, images, news, and events, to improve geolocation prediction. The system is designed to predict the geolocation of a given query, such as an image or a piece of text, by leveraging the collective information from these different data sources. A fusion framework that combines the outputs from these different components to produce a final geolocation prediction [4]

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset Description: The dataset consists of 10000 images taken from Google Street view . The dataset has 10000 png files with corresponding latitude and longitude in a csv file [5].If all the images are from Google Street View, the geolocation task may become easier. Google Street View images are taken consistently, often containing useful visual features like road signs, unique landmarks, and well-structured urban layouts. These characteristics enhance the chances of successful geolocation. However, challenges may still arise in areas where locations appear similar or in less distinctive environments, even within Street View data.

Each country's images were reverse geocoded using OpenCage API.The top 4 countries were selected namely Russia,Argentina,Australia and Brazil. Data Augmentation were performed to normalize the dataset to 2000 images per country i.e. 8000 images of final dataset.

3.2 CNN Architectures: Various custom and pre-trained CNN models were employed to assess their performance. Models included traditional architectures and recent advancements in CNN design(like Resnet50 and VGG16)

- **Feature Extraction Techniques:**

Manual Feature Extraction: Not applied due to complexity.

Automated Feature Extraction: Utilized in the CNN models, which may not capture all relevant geographic features.

4 Experiment and Results

4.1 First Custom CNN model:- The initial custom CNN model starts with a convolutional layer with 32 3x3 filters, followed by a ReLU activation function that accepts input images of size 224x224 with three colour channels. To minimise the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, a max-pooling layer with a 2x2 pool size is then applied. The model then adds a convolutional layer with 64 3x3 filters and a ReLU activation, followed by another max-pooling layer. This pattern is continued with a third convolutional layer that uses 128 3x3 filters and is followed by a max-pooling layer. Following the convolutional and pooling procedures, the model employs a Flatten layer to turn the 3D feature maps into a 1D vector, which is then fed into a dense layer with 128 units and ReLU activation for learning complex features.

The final layer is another dense layer with a number of units equal to the number of classes(4), using a softmax activation function to output the probabilities for each class. The model is compiled with the Adam optimizer and sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function, while accuracy is used as a performance metric.

Fold Number(Epoch=10)	Accuracy	Loss
1	0.552	1.5375
2	0.577	1.7322
3	0.527	1.3654
4	0.542	1.8321
5	0.528	1.6750
	Test Accuracy:-0.554	

Table 1(Corresponding Accuracy and Loss of first custom CNN model)

Figure 1(Model Accuracy and Loss of the final model<First Custom CNN>)

Challenge of Similar Images: The drop from high training accuracy to lower test accuracy suggests that the model is having difficulty generalizing when faced with new data. This aligns with our earlier observations that images from different countries often have similar features (e.g., jungles, mountains, roads), making classification difficult. The model may be memorizing the training data instead of learning meaningful patterns that generalize well.

Figure 2(Sample Images of different from dataset with high similarity)

The fact that all values are close to 1 implies that the images are visually similar to one another, at least in terms of the features extracted by the model. This might indicate that the images come from similar contexts or locations.

4.2 Second Custom CNN model:- The initial custom CNN model starts with a convolutional layer with 32 3x3 filters, followed by a ReLU activation function that accepts input images of size 224x224 with three color channels. To minimize the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, a max-pooling layer with a 2x2 pool size is applied after each convolutional layer, helping the model focus on the most prominent features. The model continues with a second convolutional layer using 64 3x3 filters and ReLU activation, followed by another max-pooling layer. This pattern is repeated for the third and fourth convolutional layers, which use 128 and 256 3x3 filters, respectively, each followed by max-pooling layers.

After the convolutional and pooling operations, the model employs a Flatten layer to convert the 3D feature maps into a 1D vector. This flattened vector is then passed through a dense layer with 512 neurons and ReLU activation, allowing the model to learn more complex features. A dropout layer is included after the dense layer to reduce overfitting by randomly dropping a fraction of the neurons during training.

The final output layer is a dense layer with a softmax activation function, and the number of neurons in this layer is equal to the number of classes (4 in this case), indicating that the model will output the probabilities for each class. The model is compiled using the Adam optimizer and the sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function, with accuracy as the performance metric.

Fold Number(Epoch=10)	Accuracy	Loss
1	0.618	0.9528
2	0.638	0.9334
3	0.628	0.9288
4	0.614	0.9235
5	0.577	1.0043
	Test Accuracy:-0.610	

Table 2 (Corresponding Accuracy and Loss of second custom CNN model)

Figure 3(Model Accuracy and Loss of the final model<second custom CNN>)

After training, our model obtained an accuracy of 61.02% on the test set. While this is a huge gain over random guessing, it does suggest that the model may fail to generalize to new data. The test loss of 0.9039 is slightly larger than the final training loss, suggesting some level of overfitting. The model performs better on training data than on unseen test data.

To deal with this different techniques such as: Data Augmentation, Hyperparameter Tunning, Cross-Validation and Regularization was applied to the dataset.

L2 Regularization	Dropout Rate	No of Epoch	Batch Size	Learning Rate	Test Accuracy	Test Loss
0.001	0.4	10	32	0.001	0.45	1.12
0.001	0.5	10	32	0.001	0.52	0.98
0.01	0.6	15	64	0.0005	0.48	1.05
0.01	0.7	15	64	0.0005	0.56	0.87
0.01	0.4	20	32	0.001	0.50	0.95

Table 3(Summary of different settings used with corresponding results)

Despite experimenting with various hyperparameter settings, including different values for L2 regularization, dropout rates, epochs, batch sizes, and learning rates, the model's accuracy consistently remained between 40% and 55% which suggests

maybe using a complex architecture such as a pretrained CNN model with a large no of layers.

4.3 Pre-trained CNN models:-

4.3.1 VGG16:- VGG16 is named for its 16 layers with learnable parameters (13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers). The depth allows the model to learn more complex features as it processes the input image

.Stopping training early as accuracy improvement is below threshold. Average cross-validation accuracy: 0.252. The average cross-validation accuracy of 25.2% and the test accuracy of 25% are quite low. This suggests that the VGG16 model is struggling to generalize well on the dataset.

Folds(Epoch 10)	Accuracy	Loss
1	0.254	1.4678
2	0.250	1.3865
	Test Accuracy:-0.250	

Table 4(Corresponding Accuracy and Loss of VGG16 CNN model)

4.3.2 ResNet50:- ResNet50 has 50 layers with learnable parameters. The depth includes convolutional layers, residual blocks, and fully connected layers. The "50" in ResNet50 refers to the number of weight layers, which is deeper than traditional networks like VGG16.

Folds(Epoch 10)	Accuracy	Loss
1	0.372	1.8515
2	0.487	1.39618
3	0.398	1.7128
	Test Accuracy:-0.405	

Table 5(Corresponding Accuracy and Loss of ResNet50 CNN model)

The moderate accuracy of custom CNN models suggests that the dataset might contain a significant number of visually similar images as seen in Figure 2, such as urban roads and jungles. These similarities can challenge the model's ability to effectively differentiate between geographical locations.

Pretrained models are typically trained on large, general datasets like ImageNet, which does not have enough similarities with our specific dataset. ImageNet images differ significantly in terms of context, features, and resolution compared to Google Street View images. As the results obtained in Table 4 and Table 5, there is a clear indication that Pretrained models might not work well with our dataset due to the differences in the visual features and characteristics between the general training data and our specific geographical images.

5 Discussion

Several obstacles arose during the experiment, particularly in differentiating visually identical photographs from different countries. One of the most problematic aspects was that geographical photographs from various places of the world frequently had similar visual characteristics. Roads, metropolitan areas, rainforests, mountains, and bodies of water, for example, can all appear remarkably similar no matter where they are. Because of this closeness in visual elements, CNN-based algorithms struggle to effectively.

This problem was obvious in the results, where custom CNN models obtained moderate accuracy (40-60%) while pretrained models such as VGG16 and ResNet50 underperformed (accuracies ranging from 20 to 40%). The pretrained models suffered since they were originally built for generic picture classification tasks and may not have acquired the minor geographical distinctions required for precise geolocation.

5.1 Proposed Solution: Leveraging Metadata

To address these issues, adding metadata could considerably improve the model's performance. Given that our dataset comprises of Google Street View photos, utilizing metadata similar to that utilised in games such as GeoGuessr [6] can considerably improve model performance. Google Street View photos frequently contain a plethora

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of contextual metadata that can be used for geolocation purposes. By focusing on geographically specific characteristics, we may differentiate seemingly identical photographs.

Since there are 4 countries in our dataset. For instance if we want to identify the country of Russia or Australia from a image some of the metadata specific to specific regions of those countries to correctly identify them are as given:-

5.1.1 Identify Australia with help of metadata through Street View:-

Within Australia wooden poles are very common, there are 4 states with around 95% composition of wooden poles [7]. Octagonal Wooden Poles are common to the region of NSW specifically around Sydney About 94% of poles in NSW are made of timber and wood. [7] .

Figure 4(Wooden/Timber Poles common in Australia)

There are road signs, markings, bollards, stop signs, speed signs that are specific to Australia or even the region of NSW which would help a model narrow down the search.

Figure 5(Common Road Signs)

Figure 6:(White outer road lines with Numbers)

Australia has a wide variety of unique Flora/Fauna to be found there with a wide variety of landscapes, ranging from desert in the center, grasslands in the south, and tropics in the north.

Figure 8(Australian vegetation, mostly dry and humid)

Figure 7:(Eucalyptus Trees:-Native to Australia)

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5.1.2 Identify Russia with help of metadata through Street View:-

Russia have specific bollards that separates it from other continent, since countries in Oceania and Americas do not use bollards. Typically those bollards are black and white which separates Russia from other European countries like France, Poland etc

Figure 9(Bollocks common in Russia)

Figure 10(curbs and guardrails can very often be painted black and white)

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Russia has blue road signs with white text on them. Most of the signs are blue but there are some red signs often with painted black on the bottom. [6]

Figure 11:(Blue and Red signs specific to Russia)

Trees in Russia can often be painted white at the bottom as an insect repellent or roadside reflector. [6]

Figure 12(White painted Trees common in Russia)

Probably the most distinctive out of all the vegetation in Russia is the famous “Hokkaido cabbage”, which in Russia grows only on the island of Sakhalin in the far east of the country. Another distinctive plant/tree is the Siberian larch, which grows only in Siberia and the Far East, and not in the rest of the country [6]:

Figure 13(Hokkaido Cabbage and Siberian Larch)

So even though the images of Russia and Australia in this instance are similar (roads and jungles) and non-localizable [2]. By leveraging the above metadata, we can separate road signs, markings, bollards, and vegetation, which helps us in distinguishing between the two countries.

These are only some of the metadata pointed out; there are metadata regarding text, license plates, city codes, highway numbers, etc. By incorporating these metadata elements, a geolocation classification model can go beyond visual similarities and focus on the unique, location-specific features that are crucial for accurate geolocation. This approach will enhance the model's ability to discern between geographically distinct areas, ultimately improving its performance in classifying images from different regions.

6 Conclusion

The outcomes of this study show that employing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for image-based geolocation tasks presents substantial obstacles, especially when discriminating between visually identical geographic places. The studies with several custom and pre-trained CNN models yielded modest accuracy (40-60%), showing that the models struggled to generalise well across varied datasets. This is mostly due to the similarity of characteristics in photographs from other countries, such as roads and forests

While CNNs excel at automated feature extraction, their capacity to identify finer features required for accurate geolocation is restricted without the addition of metadata. This work suggests that metadata, such as local landmarks, road signs, or distinctive environmental elements, could dramatically improve classification accuracy by adding additional context that CNNs alone may miss.

Future research should focus on adding such metadata to improve the model's performance, going beyond visual similarities to capture the unique, location-specific cues required for successful-geolocation.

Despite the fact that metadata integration was not implemented in this study, the prospective benefits highlighted underlines the importance of this direction in future research. By tackling these problems, we want to give insights into improving CNN-based image categorization for geographically comparable images.

7 References

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